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Applications of plasma activated waters to mitigate grapevine yellows disease

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INTRODUCTION

Grapevine sustainability is threatened by yellows phytoplasma diseases, that in Europe, are mainly “flavescence dorée” (FD) and “bois noir” (BN). With no curative treatments available, current management relies on vector control and uprooting. In this study the possibility of using plasma-activated water (PAW) for the mitigation of grapevine yellows disease was evaluated in vineyard trials. Exposing water to a plasma source results in the formation of solutions with high concentrations of reactive molecule species that act in plants as elicitors, stimulating the immune system (Zambon *et al.*, 2019, 2020; Laurita *et al.*, 2021). Grapevine plants infected by phytoplasmas and symptomatic in 2023 were treated with different types of PAW in 2024 spring and evaluated during the 2025 season.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Two vineyards of cultivar Lambrusco di Sorbara and Lambrusco Salamino, respectively (red variety) and one of Pignoletto (white variety), 5 to 7 years old were selected in fall 2023 for yellows symptoms and molecularly tested to verify the presence of phytoplasmas. In 2024 three applications were carried out in symptomatic grapevine plants in May, June and July on 120 plants with PADW (from distilled water), PATW (from tap water), and aquannolyte (from a private company). In the Pignoletto vineyard the farmer cut about 50 cm high the most symptomatic grapevine plants after the treatments. The control plants were treated with distilled and tap water respectively. All applications were performed injecting the liquids using a syringe after drilling small holes in the trunk with a sterile device. Molecular testing was performed on DNA extracted from midribs and cane scrapes collected in July-August 2025 using a CTAB-based method (Angelini *et al.*, 2001). Nested PCR amplification on 16S rRNA gene followed by RFLP analyses and/or sequencing allowed the detection and identification of phytoplasmas (Bertaccini *et al.*, 2019). Furthermore, phenological traits and symptom severity in treated and control plants were measured and statistically evaluated at a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The molecular testing on random sampling in the two cv. Lambrusco vineyards allowed to confirm the presence of 16SrV group phytoplasmas (FD) in all the three vineyards with the number of FD infected plants increased compared to the pre-treatment testing.

Figure 1. From left: distribution of symptom severity in grapevine leaf and bunches. Aquannolyte, red; control, green, and PAW, blue. Grape bunches from Pignoletto from asymptomatic and symptomatic plants. In the cv. Pignoletto vineyard the symptomatic plants low pruned in 2024, showed in the large majority, new vegetation and bunches in 2025. However, the bunches from these plants appeared of lower quality and showed insufficient sugar accumulation compared to those produced from the asymptomatic, uncut grapevine plants (Figure 1) and several phytoplasma-negative plants were detected mainly after the aquannolyte treatment. Notably, one uncut plant treated with aquannolyte remained FD-positive in both 2024 and 2025, whereas 8 out of 11 plants that were treated and cut tested negative for phytoplasma presence. From the collection of phenotypic data, only slightly differences were observed in the mean values between the diverse types of water used. In particular SPAD analysis in all treatments showed average values ranging between 32.5 and 34.5. Similarly, the analysis of symptoms observed in the leaves and in bunches did not reveal statistical differences. To highlight the effect of treatments on the phenotype, the data were analyzed grouped as PAW and control (Figure 1). Following treatment with aquannolyte and PAW, a modification in the production of vegetative and reproductive structures was observed. The number of inflorescence and sprouts remained comparable in treated plants or controls, with variations of only a few units. In contrast, the comparison between treatments revealed that, in both cases (number of inflorescences and sprouts) the control plants produced a higher number of such organs (approximately 60) compared to those treated with PAW (≈ 50) and aquannolyte (≈ 35). No significant differences were detected in SPAD values, indicating similar chlorophyll content across all treatment groups. It was possible to observe that the treated grapevines exhibited less severe symptoms compared to the control, both on leaves and grapevine bunches, for both PAWs and aquannolyte. Although the number of samples from the trials was not sufficient to draw statistically reliable conclusions, it appears that pruning alone did not influence phytoplasma containment while in the aquannolyte-treatment some reduction in the symptoms and also in phytoplasma presence was observed. These results indicate that while PAW did not significantly improve grapevine health it showed positive effects to reduce symptoms on leaves and bunches, confirming its promising role as component of integrated disease management (Perez *et al.*, 2019). These findings suggest the importance of larger sample sizes and repeated or optimized PAW applications for confirmation and optimization of the system for its scaling up in the vineyards.

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